

Year 3: Publishable Summary

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3D ICONS

<http://www.3dicons-project.eu>

Project objectives

The 3D-ICONS project started in February 2012, completing in January 2015. The project focused on digital content that included 3D models and reconstructions, enlarged models of important details and related images, texts and videos. It also includes and re-contextualizes in 3D, objects belonging to a monument but presently located elsewhere, for example in museums. The project's activities predominantly consisted of new digitisations but also included some existing 3D data, all of which has been converted into formats accessible by Europeana users. 3D-ICONS has provided Europeana with a large quantity of high-quality, 3D, well-organized and attractive information about the masterpieces of European architecture and archaeology.

The project complements the collections made available to Europeana via CARARE, Europeana Local, Athena and other projects, which developed the content base for the architectural and archaeological heritage. Another important objective was to build on the results of previous EU projects, most notably on CARARE, for the aggregation services and guidelines on the publication

Amphora, POLIMI

of 3D for Europeana, and on 3D-COFORM for the 3D creation, management and visualization tools. This has resulted in guidelines being produced as part of a complete digitisation and publication pipeline which address digitisation methodologies, post-processing and conversion to end viewer-friendly publication formats and IPR aspects. 3D-ICONS has also updated the CARARE metadata schema to accommodate 3D content and mapped this to EDM, providing guidelines and a metadata editing tool to facilitate content providers with little or no technical knowledge of XML or metadata schemas provide their 3D content to Europeana. The metadata mapping tool, MINT2 and the ingestion repository, MoRE2, were also updated for 3D applications by the project.

The target users of the 3D-ICONS content include:

- members of the general public, tourists and students who wish to be able to explore and enjoy architectural and archaeological masterpieces through Europeana which are often inaccessible to visitors either due to their remote locations or conservation management restricting access.
- The cultural institutions who are in charge of internationally and nationally important monuments and buildings, and who need tried and tested mechanisms to produce high quality 3D documentation and publish the results for Europeana as well as on their own websites.
- UNESCO and cultural institutions wishing to find new ways of delivering their missions to promote understanding and increase the sustainability of world and European heritage.
- Content providers and creative industry SMEs wishing to identify sustainable business processes and models.

Activities and Progress

The first year of the project involved substantial preparation in obtaining permission for the access to and scanning of sites and monuments before proceeding to the digitisation phase. As an illustration of the complexity of IPR for 3D cultural heritage, around half of the original content was eventually replaced with other items as well additional content being made available where IPR was not an issue. Several different scanning methods were used, from hand held scanners for the museum objects, UAVs for large monuments to LIDAR for complete sites.

UAV “Octo-copter” used by Athena-RC

Discovery Programme using a laser scanning platform on Skellig Michael

During the second year, the project partners were mainly occupied with digitising the selected sites and monuments, some of which involved trips to remote areas and archaeological sites of great importance.

One of these was Skellig Michael, a monastic settlement of stone beehive structures on a remote island abandoned around the 12th century and only accessible by boat during the summer months off the west coast of Ireland. Other sites include a Neolithic temple at Puente Tablas in Andalusia and the Holy Well of St. Cristina in Sardinia.

One of the benefits of participating in European Projects is transfer of knowledge between partners, enabling those newer to 3D technologies to improve their skills and the quality of their acquired datasets and resulting models. To this end, some of the partners have participated in training workshops to learn about the latest acquisition and modelling techniques such as the use of UAVs and photogrammetry.

One partner, MNIR of Romania, organised a national training event for other cultural heritage institutions following their attendance at a 3D summer school organised by partner FBK. The 3D-ICONS project also organised two internal metadata training workshops and a very successful technical workshop describing the different models and techniques adopted by partners at the Digital Heritage Conference hosted in Marseilles at the end of October 2013.

In order to support the complete 3D model creation process, there was also been significant developments in the infrastructure and tools. At the end of the first year, the CARARE2 metadata schema was published, having been updated to include ‘paradata’ that is specific to 3D models (e.g. dataset type, processing method, equipment and settings used, final formats). 3D-ICONS used the same infrastructure as CARARE, adapted to the new schema for ingestion to Europeana. It was also realised that a simple metadata editing tool would greatly speed up the creation of the required metadata and assist the less experienced partners in addition to providing a valuable facility for newcomers wishing to use the 3D-ICONS pipeline. Consequently, a new Metadata Editor tool has

been developed which has the advantages of creating reusable templates for each end user and producing CARARE2 compliant XML files for ingestion into MoRE2; this approach is now being adopted by other content providers to Europeana.

At month 18, the project published a report on IPR Schemes, which described the various licensing scenarios and possible solutions. It appears that Europeana's adoption of the Creative Commons licensing framework along with other prominent initiatives such as WikiLovesMonuments is having a positive impact in that this is making digital content owners pay more attention to IPR whilst also enabling them to open up access to their collections. This change in attitude was evidenced in 3D-ICONS where more organisations have started to use Creative Commons for licensing since the start of the project.

Example of visual enrichment based on the projection of textures starting from photographs finely oriented on the 3D model (CNRS-MAP)

At present, the most suitable formats are 3D-PDF for objects of low complexity (e.g. museum objects), HTML5/WebGL for objects and highly complex point cloud models, Unity3D/UnReal for less complex buildings and sites and the more complex ones where the level of detail can be optimised; and Pseudo 3D is also an option for highly complex models across the board. CNR-ISTI has employed their web-streaming viewer, 3D-HOP, for complex 3D models. It should be noted that with the current rapid changes in 3D viewing technologies, other options may become available and towards the end of the project in year 3, three of the partners started to experiment with SketchFab, making 3D models available in this latest Google technology which offers high quality, responsive viewing on the most basic of PCs.

During Year 3, the project was focussed on completing the modelling and creating the metadata for the ingestion process into Europeana, which proved to be a steep learning curve for all concerned. The project also implemented a strict quality control procedure to ensure that all content provided to Europeana was of high quality; this review process led to adjustments to the metadata to improve it and also some revisions to the publishing and viewing technologies used to meet the required standards. The project has also had a commercial impact; the Discovery Programme has made its 3D data scans available to the Star Wars film makers who used Skellig Michael as one of the locations for its latest production to enable them to accurately reproduce the site, if needed. The reports on data acquisition, post-processing and publication were also updated to take account of the latest developments in this fast-changing technological environment. Finally, the project has been widely disseminated through social media, conferences, journals and other channels. Over thirty papers have been published in conference proceedings and academic journals and articles about the project have been published in national newspapers in Spain, Ireland, the UK and Greece.

During this period, the project has also focussed upon post-processing and publication formats that are suitable for Europeana end users, publishing two reports at M21 which addressed these technical topics. “D4.1 Interim report on Post-processing” provides an overview of the main steps comprising this activity: geometric reconstruction, visual enrichment, model structuring and hypothetical reconstruction. Four case studies from the partners illustrate the variety of approaches used.

“D5.1 Publication Formats Suitable for Europeana” discusses the requirements of 3D and the challenges posed by complex 3D models for Europeana.

Main results achieved

The main results achieved to date are:

- The current inventory of monuments and buildings has been made available to Europeana, providing:
 - Over 4,200 3D models
 - Over 17,000 images
 - 245 videos,
- Where permitted, the original 3D datasets are also available for research purposes,
- An online Metadata Editor tool, which uses re-usable templates based on CARARE 2.0, has been developed for general use and is being adapted for other Europeana content projects,
- The pipeline has been documented in the Guidelines and Case Studies (D7.3) for the acquisition and production of 3D models, also made available as a print-ready PDF file,
- Comprehensive guidelines developed for managing IPR for 3D models,
- Dissemination activities have resulted in many articles and papers published, presentations at conferences and well-attended workshops at Digital Heritage, Marseilles 2013 and the final event at the Borsa Mediterranea Del Turismo Archeologico, an annual event held at a major Greco-Roman site archaeological site, Paestum in Italy.

Final results and potential impact

3D-ICONS provides a tried and tested process for the conversion and production of 3D content and the associated information which includes the technology and tools, a metadata schema tailored for 3D models, best practice guidelines for IPR and wide expertise built on many years of partner experience. This enables other cultural heritage owners of 3D content to likewise contribute their models to Europeana, raising awareness and increasing the knowledge base of all the identified stakeholders. Some examples of 3D models produced by the project are shown below.

*Geto-Dacian Helmet
from Peretu
(MNIR)*

*Point cloud of Temple-na-Skellig,
Glendalough (DISC)*

*Restored statue of
Claudio Seduto
(CISA)*

*Reconstruction of
Room 40, Villa of
Livia (CNR)*

The high quality models will also be available for other potential users; there have been expressions of interest by researchers (archaeologists, architects, restorers) in use of the 3D models and the CARARE2 metadata schema as well as a commercial application. Documentation of the production process along with other additional information about 3D models such as the different publication formats, associated IPR and options for viewing the models is available on the 3D-ICONS website. All the 3D models and all their metadata can also be viewed on the 3D-ICONS Portal at http://3d_icons.ipet.gr/. Europeana gains by being able to offer access to several thousand high quality 3D models of historic buildings and monuments, archaeological sites and related items which their end users can view these on standard computers and mobile devices.

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